
NAVIGATING FUTURE-READY ASIA-PACIFIC TVET THROUGH DIGITAL, GREEN, AND INDUSTRY INTEGRATION

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Abstract

The accelerating shift towards digitalization, sustainability, and inclusive development has intensified the transformation of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) systems across the Asia-Pacific region. This study examines the integration of digital, green, and inclusive competencies in TVET institutions by focusing on institutional practices, skills gaps, industry collaboration, innovation strategies, and implementation challenges. A descriptive-exploratory design was used based on the survey data from TVET professionals participating in a regional capacity-building program in Colombo, Sri Lanka in 2026. Findings indicate that TVET systems are in a transitional stage, with strong integration of digital learning platforms, industry-linked training, and entrepreneurship-oriented curricula; however, significant gaps remain in digital/ICT and green competencies, reflecting a mismatch between labor market demands and current training provision. Institutional practices prioritize digitalization and work-based learning, while inclusive education and governance-related competencies remain less developed, and industry collaboration is largely limited to internships and training with weaker engagement in research, innovation, and commercialization. Key barriers include limited funding, insufficient faculty expertise, and inadequate infrastructure for digital, green, and inclusive TVET, while respondents highlight the importance of public-private partnerships, qualifications frameworks, and industry-driven initiatives. Regional cooperation, particularly through joint research, cross-border exchange, and qualifications harmonization, is identified as a key enabler of transformation. The study concludes that while Asia-Pacific TVET systems are increasingly aligning with digital, green, and inclusive agendas, they remain constrained by structural and capacity limitations, requiring a more integrated ecosystem-based approach to strengthen institutional readiness, workforce competencies, industry collaboration, and regional cooperation toward a future-ready TVET system aligned with Industry 5.0 and the Sustainable Development Goals.

Key Words: TVET, Digital Transformation, Green Skills, Inclusive Education, Industry 5.0, Asia-Pacific Skills Development, Regional Cooperation

1. INTRODUCTION

The recent turn of events in the Middle East has created a massive impact on how nations are looking at the potential of integrating green and sustainable practices in maintaining the economic and financial stability across all regions (Energy Tracker Asia, 2024; New Security Beat, 2026). Facing the backlash of the growing global energy crisis leading to the decline of the economic performance of several countries worldwide, this pressing situation poses a greater risk resulting in economic downturn and inflation due to persisting geoeconomic confrontation (Asian Development Bank, 2024; World Bank, 2024). The tension

which surfaced from these developments further emphasized the need for countries to reevaluate their dependence on traditional energy sources, and to fast track the transition towards a more sustainable and resilient system.

As this global predicament continues to escalate, the International Energy Agency (IEA) has predicted that the international gas prices can go up to 160% which will eventually pull the global growth down to 2.5% and increase the inflation rate to 5.2% (World Economic Forum, 2025). In the Asia-Pacific (APAC) landscape, this overdependence on fossil fuels is threatening the energy security in the region. In the Philippines alone, around 85% of its primary energy is derived from oil, gas, and coal which are sourced from the Middle East. Meanwhile in Thailand, it was recorded that 96% of its energy consumption is dependent on fossil fuels with only 1.5% being generated from solar and wind to address the country's demand. In most cases, countries across the region would opt to consume imported and costly fossil fuels despite the availability of alternative yet local renewable sources.

Simultaneously, digital transformation is creating a promising pathway for traditional industries to accelerate their shift towards globalization especially in Asia and the Pacific (OECD, 2023; World Bank, 2019). This can be attributed to the increasing demand for digital skills in the labor market, the need for flexible and more accessible learning models, and the rise of Industry 4.0 and 5.0. However, the digital divide remains to be a key challenge among nations especially in rural and disadvantaged areas (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2022). Not to mention the significant disparities in infrastructure readiness, digital literacy, and institutional capacity.

At the same time, with the shift towards green economies, the Asia-Pacific region strategically lies amidst the heart of the biodiversity and nature loss crisis (UNESCAP, 2024; Temasek et al., 2023). Given the pressing situation, governments and industries are integrating sustainability principles into their production systems, energy use, and workforce development. However, despite its growing recognition, the implementation of green skills development remains uneven with a significant number of institutions that are still within the early stages of embedding environmental competencies in their existing curricula and training programs.

Under these circumstances, the regional Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) systems play a critical role in capacitating our future-ready workforce to effectively adapt to the rapidly evolving industrial, environmental, and technological demands of the 21st century (UNESCO, 2021; ILO, 2026). The responsibility of upholding the digital, green, and industrial transformation lies firstly on the TVET institutions as they endeavor to produce graduates who are not only equipped with the much needed technical competencies but also with digital literacy, sustainability-oriented skills, innovation capabilities and adaptive lifelong learning competencies. Hence, the integration of digitalization, green transformation, and industry collaboration within the professional TVET community has been quintessential in forging workforce resilience, championing inclusive economic growth, and in enhancing regional competitiveness across APAC.

As the world turns its lens on workforce development that is beyond automation and efficiency but leaning more towards a more human-centered, sustainable, and resilient industrial ecosystem through the emergence of Industry 5.0, TVET institutions are called upon to redesign their curricula, strengthen industry partnerships, modernize their training delivery mechanisms, and foster interdisciplinary competencies that are aligned with the future labor market demands. Nevertheless, all the relevant stakeholders including governments, industries, and educational institutions must synergize and work

together to establish a responsive and future-oriented TVET ecosystems that are capable of addressing the interrelated and interconnected challenges of digital disruption, environmental sustainability, and economic transformation.

Hence, this paper examines how the Asia-Pacific TVET systems navigates the challenges of future-readiness through the strategic integration of digital transformation, green skills development, and industry engagement. Specifically, this study analyzes the emerging trends, existing challenges, and transformative opportunities that can shape the TVET systems in the region in terms of institutional innovation, policy support, and regional collaboration in building resilient and sustainable workforce development frameworks.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-exploratory research design to examine the emerging practices, challenges, and opportunities that are related to digital, green, and inclusive TVET systems in the Asia-Pacific region (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2022). It gathered insights from the participants of the Regional Program on *Transforming TVET for a Digital, Green, and Inclusive Economy* conducted from March 23-27, 2026 in Sri Lanka. A total of twenty (20) participants which are composed of TVET leaders, administrators, instructors, lecturers, and policymakers from various Asia-Pacific countries participated in the study. The descriptive-exploratory approach enabled the researchers to capture the institutional perspectives and contextual insights regarding digital transformation, green skills integration, inclusive practices, industry collaboration, and institutional readiness within TVET systems. Although limited in sample size, the study prioritized the depth and relevance of practitioner experiences and professional perspectives rather than statistical generalization.

2.2 Study Context

The Asia-Pacific region continues to face numerous challenges in transforming its TVET systems to become more responsive to digitalization, sustainability, and inclusivity demands (Asian Development Bank, 2024; UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2022). Significant issues such as limited digital infrastructure, inadequate institutional capacity, weak industry linkages, uneven policy implementation, and insufficient integration of green and inclusive practices are continuously affecting the effectiveness and relevance of TVET across the region (ADB, 2021; UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2022). Unfortunately, these challenges are further exacerbated by rapid technological disruptions, changing labor market requirements, and growing pressures to align with the workforce development systems within the scope of Industry 5.0 and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Given the gravity of these circumstances, governments, industries, and educational institutions in APAC have resorted to the strategic prioritization of TVET transformation towards digital, green, and inclusive economies (ILO, 2022; UNESCO, 2021). The integration of digital technologies, green skills development, inclusive education practices, and industry-responsive learning models has become important in the preparation of a future-ready workforce that is highly capable of adapting to the evolving socio-economic and environmental conditions. Within this context, TVET institutions are gradually moving from the traditional teaching and training approaches to a modern and innovative pedagogy that is powered by digital platforms, technology-enabled learning systems, industry collaborations, and

sustainability-oriented training frameworks. In addition to this, TVET institutions are gradually innovating beyond traditional teaching and training approaches through the utilization of digital platforms, technology-enabled learning systems, industry collaborations, and sustainability-oriented training frameworks.

This paper aimed to assess the emerging practices, challenges, and opportunities that are associated with future-ready TVET transformation across the participating CPSC member countries. Instead of seeking statistical generalization, this exploratory study focused on analytical depth and contextual understanding of how digital, green, and inclusive TVET transformation is presently implemented, experienced, and perceived by the regional program participants in their respective TVET institution and their current country practice. The insights generated from this context provided a grounded understanding of the institutional realities, opportunities, constraints, and strategic considerations that are associated with developing future-ready TVET systems in the Asia-Pacific region.

2.3 Data Sources

This study drew on multiple sources of evidence so as to support an in-depth exploratory analysis of the emerging practices, challenges, and opportunities that are related to digital, green, and inclusive TVET transformation in the Asia-Pacific region. A structured survey was administered to the participants of the Regional Program on *Transforming TVET for a Digital, Green, and Inclusive Economy* conducted from March 23-27, 2026 that was organized by Colombo Plan Staff College (CPSC) in collaboration with the Ministry of Education, Higher Education and Vocational Education of Sri Lanka. The survey captured the participants' demographics and gathered their insights on the following key areas: institutional effectiveness in integrating digital, green, and inclusive TVET practices; existing skill gaps among learners; implementation of innovative teaching and learning practices; industry collaboration mechanisms; institutional readiness for Industry 5.0; and challenges encountered in transforming TVET systems. A total of twenty (20) respondents completed the survey, all of whom held leadership, administrative, instructional, policy-related, or TVET delivery roles within their respective institutions and organizations across the Asia-Pacific region. The secondary data were obtained from the program-related documents, thematic papers, institutional references, and relevant literature that are associated with digital transformation, Green TVET, inclusive education, Industry 4.0 and 5.0, sustainable development, and regional qualifications frameworks. These sources provided conceptual grounding and contextual support for the interpretation and analysis of the study findings.

3. SAMPLING AND DATA COLLECTION

This study utilized a purposive sampling method in which the respondents were selected through their direct involvement in TVET leadership, administration, instruction, policy implementation, and institutional development across the participating Asia-Pacific countries (ILO, 2026). The respondents were also participants of the Regional Program on *Transforming TVET for a Digital, Green, and Inclusive Economy* that was conducted by CPSC.

By actively engaging individuals who are directly involved in TVET governance, curriculum implementation, digital transformation initiatives, industry partnerships, and institutional management, the researchers were able to capture the informed insights regarding the emerging practices, challenges, and opportunities that are associated with digital, green, and inclusive TVET transformation in the Asia-Pacific region.

The following are the demographic profiles of the respondents who participated in study.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of Survey Respondents (n=20)

Variable	Categories	Frequency
Country	Bhutan	1
	Fiji	1
	Malaysia	2
	Maldives	1
	Myanmar	1
	Nepal	1
	Pakistan	1
	Philippines	2
	Sri Lanka	10
Gender	Female	8
	Male	12
Age	25-34	3
	35-44	7
	45-54	9
	55-64	1
Designation	Assistant Director	3
	Director	2
	Principal	2
	Instructor	2
	Assistant Professor II	1
	Associate Professor	1
	Deputy Chief Engineer	1

	Deputy Director	1
	Head, Electrical & Electronic Technology	1
	Head, Computer Science	1
	Lecturer	1
	Program Officer	1
	Senior ICT Technician	1
	Senior Lecturer	1
	Supervising TESD Specialist	1
Institution	Ceylon-German Technical Training Institute (CGTTI), Sri Lanka	1
	Council for Technical Education and Vocational Training (CTECT), Nepal	1
	Department of Technical Education and Vocational Training (DTET), Sri Lanka	1
	Department of Technical Education and Training-College of Technology, Rathnapura (DTET-COT Rathnapura), Sri Lanka	1
	Government Technical High School (GTHS), Taungoo, Myanmar	1
	Malaysia (Unspecified)	1
	Malaysian Research Institute for Vocational Education and Training (MyRIVET), University Tun Hussein Onn, Malaysia	1
	Ministry of Education and Skills Development (MNSDA), Bhutan	1
	National Vocational and Technical Training	1

	Commission (NAVTTTC), Pakistan	
	National Institute of Business Management (NIBM), Sri Lanka	1
	Ocean University of Sri Lanka	1
	Sri-Lanka-German Training Institute, Kilinochchi	1
	TESDA Women's Center	1
	TESDA-Quezon National Agricultural School	1
	University of Vocational Technology	2
	Vocational Training Authority	1
	Vocational Training Authority (VTA), Sri Lanka	1
	Waidana College, Ministry of Education, Fiji	1

A total of twenty (20) participants successfully completed the structured survey. Although limited in number, the sample size reflects the exploratory and contextual nature of the study, emphasizing the analytical depth and practitioner perspectives rather than statistical generalization. The responses were collected directly from the participants to ensure accurate representation of their institutional experiences, perceptions, and challenges that are related to digital transformation, green skills integration, inclusive practices, Industry 5.0 readiness, and regional cooperation within their respective TVET systems. This approach enabled a focused examination of institutional realities, governance mechanisms, and strategic opportunities for strengthening future-ready TVET systems across the Asia-Pacific region.

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

This section presents the key findings of the study in relation to the transformation of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) systems towards digital, green, and inclusive economies in the Asia-Pacific region. Drawing primarily on the results of the structured survey, the discussion assesses the institutional readiness, emerging skill gaps, innovative and industry-driven practices, governance mechanisms, and challenges that were encountered in integrating digital technologies, green skills, and inclusive approaches within TVET systems. These findings further expose the participants' perspectives on regional cooperation, policy support, and institutional strategies aimed at strengthening future-ready TVET systems that are aligned with Industry 4.0 and 5.0. These insights are then situated within the broader context of regional TVET transformation initiatives, sustainable workforce development, and institutional readiness frameworks in order to evaluate the extent to which existing policies, institutional

capacities, and collaborative mechanisms support or constrain the advancement of digital, green, and inclusive TVET across the Asia-Pacific region (OECD, 2023; World Bank, 2019).

Table 2. Skills Gap Evident Among Learners in TVET Institutions

Skill Gap	Frequency	% of Respondents
Digital/ICT Skills	12	60
Green Skills	11	55
Inclusive Skills	10	50
Adaptive/Learning-to-Learn Skills	6	30
Entrepreneurial Skills	6	30
Soft Skills	5	25

Table 2 reveals that the most prominent skills gap among learners in TVET institutions is in digital/ICT skills as reported by 12 respondents (60%). This indicates the persistent deficiencies in digital literacy and the application of emerging technologies despite the increasing digitization of education and industry. This is closely followed by green skills, identified by 11 respondents (55%). This highlights the limited learner preparedness in areas such as sustainability, renewable energy, and climate-resilient practices, which are increasingly essential in the region's transition toward low-carbon economies. Inclusive skills were also noted as a significant gap by 10 respondents (50%). This suggests that TVET systems are still facing challenges in adequately addressing equity, accessibility, and the needs of marginalized groups in line with inclusive development goals. Meanwhile, both adaptive or learning-to-learn skills and entrepreneurial skills were reported by 6 respondents (30%) each thus, reflecting gaps in learners' capacity for self-directed learning, innovation, and enterprise development, which are critical in rapidly evolving labor markets. Soft skills such as communication, teamwork, and interpersonal competencies were also identified by 5 respondents (25%), representing the least frequently reported but still relevant gap affecting workplace readiness. These findings suggest a multi-dimensional skills deficit in TVET systems, with digital and green competencies emerging as the most urgent areas for development in response to the ongoing digital, green, and inclusive transformation across the Asia-Pacific region.

Table 3: Integration of Digital and Green Curriculum in the Regional TVET Institutions

Practice	Frequency	% of Respondents
Digital Learning Platforms and Online Training Modules	14	70
Industry-linked Projects or Internships	13	65
Green Skills Integration (Sustainability, Eco-Innovation, Circular Economy)	12	60
Entrepreneurship Modules	12	60
Policy & Governance Literacy for TVET Leaders	7	35

Social Inclusion & Equity Initiatives	6	30
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Table 3 demonstrates the extent to which digital and green curriculum practices are integrated within regional TVET institutions as perceived by the respondents. The most widely implemented practice is the use of digital learning platforms and online training modules as reported by 14 respondents (70%). This showcases a strong shift toward technology-enabled teaching and learning approaches across institutions. This is followed by industry-linked projects or internships with 13 reported respondents (65%). This reflects the sustained efforts to strengthen work-based learning and improve alignment between TVET provision and labor market needs. Both green skills integration (including sustainability, eco-innovation, and circular economy concepts) and entrepreneurship modules were cited by 12 respondents (60%) each which suggest that a majority of institutions are increasingly embedding sustainability-oriented and enterprise-focused competencies into their curricula, although full mainstreaming is still in progress. In contrast, policy and governance literacy for TVET leaders was noted by 7 respondents (35%), while social inclusion and equity initiatives were reported by 6 respondents (30%). These results expose that although digital and industry-related innovations are relatively more advanced, governance capacity-building and structured inclusion efforts remain less extensively integrated across institutions. These reflect a gradual but uneven integration of digital, green, and inclusive curriculum practices within regional TVET systems, with stronger emphasis on digitalization and industry linkage compared to governance and inclusion dimensions.

Table 4. Innovative Practices or Programs Promoting Digital TVET Learning in Institutions

Innovative Practice/Program	Frequency	% of Respondents
Industry Mentorship and Project Collaboration	14	70
Digital Platforms & Simulations for Learning	12	60
Green Innovation Labs/Sustainability Projects	9	45
Inclusive Curriculum Modules Targeting Marginalized Groups	7	35
Hackathons or Innovation Challenges	5	25

Table 4 illustrates the innovative practices and programs that promote digital TVET learning across the participating institutions. The most commonly reported initiative is industry mentorship and project collaboration which were identified by 14 respondents (70%). This reveals the strong role of industry engagement in enhancing applied learning, workplace relevance, and innovation-oriented competencies among learners. This is followed by the use of digital platforms and simulations for learning as reported by 12 respondents (60%). This result highlights the growing reliance on technology-enhanced instructional tools to support flexible, interactive, and practice-based learning environments. Green innovation labs and sustainability projects were identified by 9 respondents (45%). This indicates a moderate level of institutional effort to integrate environmental sustainability and applied green technologies into TVET learning experiences. Inclusive curriculum modules targeting marginalized groups were reported by 7 respondents (35%) which suggests that while inclusivity is being addressed in some institutions, its integration into structured curriculum innovation remains limited. Hackathons or innovation challenges were the least frequently reported at 5 respondents (25%). This reveals that more experimental and competition-based learning approaches are still emerging rather than widely

institutionalized across the region. These findings suggest that while industry collaboration and digital learning tools are relatively well established, more advanced innovation-driven and inclusivity-focused practices remain at an early stage of implementation in regional TVET institutions.

Table 5. Industry Collaboration Mechanism Supporting Digital, Green, and Inclusive TVET

Collaboration Mechanism	Frequency	% of Respondents
Internship Programs	16	80
Industry-Led Workshops/Training	15	75
Joint R&D Project	6	30
Mentorship Programs	5	25
Commercialization of Student Innovations	3	15

Table 5 documents the industry collaboration mechanisms that support the implementation of digital, green, and inclusive TVET across the participating institutions. The results indicate that internship programs are the most dominant form of collaboration as reported by 16 respondents (80%). This underscores the strong emphasis on work-based learning as a key strategy for enhancing learner exposure to real industry environments and improving employability outcomes. This is closely followed by industry-led workshops and training activities with 15 identified respondents (75%). This reflects the active engagement of industry partners in providing technical inputs, skills upgrading, and practical knowledge transfer to TVET institutions. However, more advanced forms of collaboration such as joint research and development (R&D) projects were identified by only 6 respondents (30%) which implies that limited institutional capacity or industry alignment for collaborative innovation initiatives. Mentorship programs were determined by 5 respondents (25%) which indicates that structured long-term guidance from industry professionals remains relatively underdeveloped in many institutions. Meanwhile, commercialization of student innovations recorded the lowest frequency at 3 respondents (15%). This highlights that the translation of student outputs into market-ready products or services is still in its early stages across the region. These results suggest that while foundational industry engagement mechanisms such as internships and training are well established, deeper forms of collaboration that foster innovation, commercialization, and sustained mentorship remain limited within regional TVET systems.

Table 6. Challenges Hindering the Integration of Digital, Green, and Inclusive TVET

Challenge	Frequency	% of Respondents
Limited Funding/Resources	12	60
Low Faculty Expertise in Digital, Green, or Inclusive TVET	11	55
Absence of Proper Infrastructure (Labs, Green Tech, Assistive Devices)	11	55
Weak Industry Linkages	5	25
Low Student Engagement or Motivation	5	25

Policy/Regulatory Limitations	4	20
Rural Area Implementation Challenges	1	5

Table 6 indicates the key challenges hindering the integration of digital, green, and inclusive TVET across the participating institutions. The most frequently cited barrier is limited funding and resources which was noted by 12 respondents (60%). This points out that financial constraints remain a critical limitation in upgrading infrastructure, acquiring digital tools, and implementing sustainability-oriented training initiatives. This is closely followed by low faculty expertise in digital, green, or inclusive TVET and the absence of proper infrastructure (such as laboratories, green technologies, and assistive devices) with 11 respondents (55%) each. These signal the interrelated challenges of human resource capacity and institutional readiness that significantly affect the effective delivery of modernized TVET programs. Weak industry linkages and low student engagement or motivation were both reported by 5 respondents (25%) which indicate that gaps in external collaboration and learner participation continue to constrain the full realization of industry-responsive and learner-centered TVET systems. Policy and regulatory limitations were determined by 4 respondents (20%), showcasing the concerns regarding the adequacy and responsiveness of existing governance frameworks in supporting innovation and transformation in TVET. Meanwhile, rural area implementation challenges were the least reported at 1 respondent (5%), indicating that while geographic disparities exist, they were less emphasized among the respondents in this particular sample. The findings suggest that structural constraints related to funding, institutional capacity, and infrastructure remain the most pressing challenges to advancing digital, green, and inclusive TVET in the Asia-Pacific region.

Table 7. Effective Policies and Initiatives Enhancing Digital, Green, and Inclusive TVET

Policy/Initiative	Frequency	% of Respondents
Public-Private Partnerships	12	60
Industry-Driven Training Programs	13	65
National/Regional Qualifications Frameworks	12	60
Scholarships or Incentives for Students	11	55

Table 7 portrays the policies and initiatives perceived by respondents as most effective in enhancing digital, green, and inclusive TVET systems. The findings reveal that industry-driven training programs are the most frequently cited initiative as reported by 13 respondents (65%). This underscores the critical role of industry participation in ensuring the relevance, responsiveness, and practical orientation of TVET delivery. This is closely followed by public-private partnerships and national/regional qualifications frameworks, both identified by 12 respondents (60%), highlighting the importance of collaborative governance structures and standardized competency frameworks in strengthening alignment between education systems and labor market needs across the region. Scholarships and student incentives were chosen by 11 respondents (55%). This implies the continued relevance of financial support mechanisms in promoting equitable access to TVET and encouraging participation in priority skills areas, including digital and green competencies. These outcomes corroborate the fact that policy effectiveness in advancing digital, green, and inclusive TVET is strongly associated with multi-stakeholder collaboration, particularly through industry engagement and structured qualification systems, complemented by targeted financial support to learners. These findings emphasize the need for sustained policy coherence and

strengthened partnerships among governments, industries, and training institutions to accelerate TVET transformation in line with regional development priorities and the demands of Industry 5.0.

Table 8. Strategies Strengthening Regional Collaboration for Digital, Green, and Inclusive TVET

Strategy	Frequency	% of Respondents
Cross-Border Teacher/Trainer Exchange Programs	15	75
Joint Research & Innovation Projects	17	85
Sharing of Best Practices and Curriculum Frameworks	15	75
Regional Qualifications Recognition	14	70
Regional Policy Harmonization	14	70

Table 8 reveals the strategies that were identified by respondents as most effective in strengthening regional collaboration for digital, green, and inclusive TVET across the Asia-Pacific region. The most frequently cited strategy is joint research and innovation projects which was reported by 17 respondents (85%). This signals a strong consensus on the importance of collaborative knowledge production and innovation as a driver for advancing TVET transformation at the regional level. This is followed by cross-border teacher/trainer exchange programs and the sharing of best practices and curriculum frameworks, both identified by 15 respondents (75%). This pinpoints the perceived value of mobility, peer learning, and the dissemination of effective pedagogical and institutional models in enhancing TVET quality and responsiveness.

Regional qualifications recognition and regional policy harmonization were each cited by 14 respondents (70%) thus, highlighting the need for greater alignment of standards, competencies, and policy directions to facilitate workforce mobility, mutual recognition of skills, and stronger regional integration.

These findings suggest that the respondents place a strong emphasis on collaborative innovation, capacity-building exchanges, and harmonized frameworks as key enablers of regional TVET transformation. These results also underscore the importance of strengthening institutional partnerships and policy convergence to support a more integrated, future-ready, and resilient TVET ecosystem in the Asia-Pacific region, aligned with the demands of digitalization, sustainability, and inclusive development.

5. DISCUSSION

The findings of the study exposes a multidimensional transformation landscape within TVET systems across the Asia-Pacific region, particularly in relation to digitalization, green skills integration, inclusivity, and industry engagement. Overall, the results reveal that while significant progress has been made in adopting digital and industry-linked practices, several structural and capacity-related gaps continue to hinder the full realization of future-ready TVET systems aligned with Industry 5.0 and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

A key finding of the study is the persistent skills gap among learners, particularly in digital/ICT and green competencies. This reflects a critical mismatch between evolving labor market demands and current TVET outputs, where technological advancement and sustainability transitions are outpacing curriculum

and instructional reforms. The prominence of digital skills gaps suggests that despite increasing adoption of digital learning platforms, learner proficiency in applying digital tools, emerging technologies, and data-driven practices remains insufficient. Similarly, the significant gap in green skills underscores the early stage of integration of sustainability-related competencies within TVET systems, particularly in areas such as renewable energy, climate resilience, and circular economy practices. These results reinforce the need for accelerated curriculum modernization and stronger alignment between TVET provision and the green and digital transitions occurring across the region.

The study also reveals that TVET institutions are progressively integrating digital learning platforms, industry-linked training, and entrepreneurship modules into their curricula. This indicates a growing shift toward blended learning environments and work-integrated education models that enhance employability and practical relevance. However, the relatively lower integration of policy and governance literacy, as well as social inclusion initiatives, suggests that institutional transformation is still uneven. While technical and industry-oriented innovations are advancing, governance capacity-building and structured inclusion strategies remain less developed, highlighting a gap between operational innovation and systemic reform.

In terms of innovative practices, the strong emphasis on industry mentorship and project collaboration demonstrates the central role of industry engagement in shaping competency-based and applied learning approaches. This finding aligns with global trends emphasizing work-based learning as a core pillar of TVET transformation. However, the limited adoption of hackathons, innovation challenges, and inclusive curriculum models indicates that more experimental, learner-centered, and equity-focused pedagogies are still emerging rather than institutionalized across the region. This reveals that while foundational collaboration with industry is well established, deeper innovation ecosystems within TVET institutions are still evolving.

The results further show that internships and industry-led training remain the dominant mechanisms of collaboration between TVET institutions and industry partners. This reflects a strong operational linkage that supports skills development and workplace exposure. However, the relatively low engagement in joint research and development, mentorship programs, and commercialization of student innovations indicates that industry collaboration is still largely training-oriented rather than innovation-driven. This limits the potential of TVET systems to function as active contributors to regional innovation ecosystems and knowledge economies.

The challenges identified in the study further explain these gaps in transformation. Limited funding and resources, coupled with insufficient faculty expertise and inadequate infrastructure, emerge as the most significant barriers to implementing digital, green, and inclusive TVET. These constraints point to systemic capacity limitations that affect both the quality and scalability of reforms. Weak industry linkages, policy limitations, and low student engagement further compound these challenges, indicating that TVET transformation requires not only curriculum reform but also stronger institutional ecosystems, policy coherence, and stakeholder engagement.

Despite these challenges, the study draws attention to several enabling policies and initiatives that support TVET transformation, particularly industry-driven training programs, public-private partnerships, and qualifications frameworks. These mechanisms demonstrate the importance of multi-stakeholder governance in ensuring relevance, quality, and responsiveness of TVET systems. The role of scholarships

and incentives also underscores the continued importance of equity-focused interventions in expanding access to skills development opportunities.

Finally, the study validates the critical importance of regional collaboration in advancing digital, green, and inclusive TVET systems. Respondents strongly emphasized joint research and innovation, cross-border exchange programs, and harmonization of qualifications frameworks as key strategies for strengthening regional integration. These also imply that future-ready TVET transformation in the Asia-Pacific region cannot be achieved in isolation but requires sustained cooperation, knowledge sharing, and policy alignment among countries. Such collaboration is essential for building a more coherent, responsive, and resilient regional TVET ecosystem capable of supporting Industry 5.0 transitions and sustainable development goals.

The outcome of this study illustrates a region in transition where significant strides in digitalization and industry engagement coexist with persistent gaps in skills readiness, inclusivity, governance capacity, and innovation ecosystems. This duality affirms the need for a more integrated and systemic approach to TVET transformation, one that simultaneously advances technological adoption, sustainability integration, inclusive practices, and regional cooperation.

6. CONCLUSION

This study examined the emerging practices, challenges, and opportunities that are associated with the transformation of TVET systems towards digital, green, and inclusive economies in the Asia-Pacific region. It also provides a contextual understanding of how TVET institutions are responding to the demands of digitalization, sustainability transitions, inclusivity, and Industry 5.0.

The findings reveal that while there is notable progress in the integration of digital learning platforms, industry-linked training, and entrepreneurship-oriented curricula, significant gaps remain in learners' digital and green competencies. These gaps reflect a broader misalignment between rapidly evolving labor market demands and the current capacity of TVET systems to respond effectively. In addition, although institutions are increasingly engaging with industry through internships and training programs, more advanced forms of collaboration such as joint research, innovation, and commercialization of outputs remain limited.

The research further stresses the persistent structural and institutional challenges, particularly in relation to funding constraints, inadequate infrastructure, and limited faculty capacity in delivering digital, green, and inclusive TVET. These challenges continue to hinder the scalability and sustainability of reform initiatives across the region. Despite these limitations, the presence of enabling policy frameworks such as public-private partnerships, qualifications frameworks, and industry-driven training programs indicates a growing policy commitment toward strengthening TVET systems.

Importantly, this exposes the critical role of regional cooperation in advancing TVET transformation. Strong consensus among respondents on the importance of joint research, cross-border exchange programs, and harmonization of qualifications frameworks reflects the need for deeper regional integration to support knowledge sharing, capacity development, and policy alignment.

Overall, the study concludes that the TVET systems in the Asia-Pacific region are in a transitional phase as characterized by the growing adoption of digital and industry-responsive practices, yet constrained by structural, institutional, and capacity-related limitations (World Economic Forum, 2025; UNESCO, 2021).

Addressing these gaps requires a more holistic and integrated approach that strengthens institutional readiness, enhances faculty and learner competencies, deepens industry engagement, and promotes sustained regional collaboration. Such efforts are essential to ensure that TVET systems remain relevant, resilient, and responsive to the demands of a rapidly evolving global economy shaped by digital transformation, green transitions, and inclusive development imperatives.

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